

The 140 Characters Are Setting the Agenda of the Day: A Critical analysis of Role of twitter in Lalitgate

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ABSTRACT –

The face of a news room in India has been changed radically with the ever growing popularity of social media, where it sets agenda for the news organizations to follow. The #Lalitgate is a classical example, where the Ex IPL Commissioner, Lalit Modi, who has gained a notorious image due to his controversies, broke news on twitter, from there it has been picked up by 24x7 news channels, subsequently online portals do a piece on it, again there is a prime time discussion on that news, followed by a morning coverage by the news papers.

As a person gain ability to create sensationalism, he utilizes the ability of social media to create some dialogues, with a larger worldwide audience, which was earlier not possible due to the monologue approach of traditional media. The ability of that piece of information to get retweeted by followers allows it to trend high on twitter. As the number become astonishing some time, it automatically qualifies for the attention of the editors of media organizations and eventually sets the agenda of the day.

The social media platforms; Twitter, Facebook, Whatsapp etc. have become the essential tool of news gathering of a modern news room. Twitter with its 302 million followers worldwide, eventually became a credible online source of news gathering as the tweets are usually came through a first person, citing his/her views or, opinion on a subject matter.

This research paper aims to critically analyze the role of twitter as an agenda setting tool in #Lalitgate, where, the cricket administrator turned whistleblower, Lalit Modi, used twitter effectively for his revelations, and he not only trolled successfully on twitter but news media as well. The scope of this paper is limited to the media coverage by English medium news channels and papers only.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY:

The objective of this paper is to examine the role of twitter as an agenda setting tool for mass media. The original agenda setting tool propelled by McCombs and Shaw (1972) observed a major correlation between the public perception of key issues and the mass media's focus on that issue. The key finding of the research suggested that the media though not necessarily tells the people "what to think" but tells "what to think about". People form their own opinion about issues based on their political or moral belief. However, with the advent of social media, the popular public discourses and sometime the deliberate attempt by an individual form the agenda for the mass media. What we are witnessing is an interesting trend where, social media is partially sharing the role of agenda setting with mass media. This paper will first define the agenda setting and then dig into the popular social media site "Twitter" and its role in agenda setting for mass media based on the incident of #Lalitgate. Finally, this paper seeks to answer the question that "Is the role of agenda setting is shifting from mass media to social media?"

INTRODUCTION:

Media is assumed to be the fourth state of democracy, and to some believer social media is the fifth state, which empowered a common citizen to engage in a dialogue that was otherwise restricted to a monologue in the case of traditional media. Traditional media is somehow perceived biased in its role of opinion maker by the champions of social media. The tools of social media like Facebook and Twitter are the new temples of democracy, where one can

go inside without any restriction of cast and creed, and perform the rituals of worshipping according to their faith.

What led to the #Lalitgate?

Lalit Modi was the Commissioner of IPL in 2009, when the T20 cricket tournament was held in South Africa. Modi allegedly flouted the rules of foreign exchange regulation during that tournament. He flew to UK avoiding an investigation against him in India, by claiming that he faces threat to his life in India.

The then UPA government at the Centre revoked his passport and had pressed for his extradition from UK and also told British government that India-UK relation would get affected if UK helps Modi.

Lalit Modi challenged this decision in Delhi High Court and also asked the British Government for a travel document. In 2014, Modi asked the British Govt for a travel document to be able to travel to Portugal where his wife has been suffering from breast cancer and was scheduled to go for a surgery in Portugal on Aug 4, 2014.

Controversy over Sushma Swaraj and Lalit Modi made headlines on Sunday, June 14, 2015, when a news channel 'Times Now' disclosed an email chain which showed that Sushma Swaraj, the external affair minister, had spoken to Indian-origin British MP Keith Vaz, to issue the travel documents to Lalit Modi. She allegedly told Vaz that British Government can follow its laws and rules in such a situation and India-UK relation will not get affected if UK issues travel documents to Lalit Modi.

Vaz allegedly cited Swaraj's name to put pressure on UK's top immigration official to grant British travel papers to Lalit Modi. In the aftermath, Modi reportedly received the documents in less than 24 hours. Vaz also offered to help Swaraj's nephew Jyotirmay Kaushal to apply for a British law degree course at Sussex University.

Later Swaraj denied the allegations against her stating that the help was extended on humanitarian ground to a husband for surgery of his wife suffering from Cancer? After his wife's surgery, he came back to London. What is it that I changed?" "Regarding Jyotirmay Kaushal's admission, she tweeted that he secured admission through the normal admission process."

The friend list of Lalit Modi includes, Prince Andrew, Raul Castro, former Interpol boss Ronald Noble, Naomi Campbell, Paris Hilton, Keith Vaz and scores of others. Sitting in the picturesque Balkan region of Montenegro, Lalit Modi replied to a question that whether Foreign Minister Sushma Swaraj helped him with British authorities, allowing him to travel to Lisbon, Portugal, "what was really wrong"? Don't friends help each other? Modi also introduced a document in which Chief Minister of Rajasthan Vasundhara Raje was shown testifying for him in a British court as a testament to his credentials as a good man. After that, he went on shredding reputations and challenging his detractors through series of tweets and

dropping names of senior politicians and others in what has now infamously known as #Lalitgate.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Agenda Setting

The Agenda-Setting is a key communication theory, developed in 1972 by McCombs & Shaw, and focuses on mass media effects on the public. The theory states that the media have a great influence on what is on the public's agenda, what they talk about and what they find important, by acting as the gatekeepers for what news is shared through them.

McCombs and Shaw followed the 1968 American Presidential Election Campaign and compared voter's perception about the key issues to the published and broadcasted content by the mass media. McCombs and Shaw concluded that mass media suggests the people "what to think about", however people still form their perception according to their political or moral beliefs.

Brosius and Weimann (1996) challenged this notion of flow of agenda message from mass media to public, and suggested an alternative of flow from the public to the media as well within the public. In their work, there is a significant indication of role of interpersonal communication and public discourse in the process of agenda setting.

RESEARCH METHOD:

To understand the role of social media (twitter in case of this paper) in agenda setting for mass media the researcher has performed content analysis of social media and mass media. Tweeter handles of journalists (like Rajdeep Sardesai, Rahul Kanwal etc.), news organizations (like Times Now, India Today etc.) and Lalit Modi were thoroughly investigated to derive the correlation between the tweet, news headlines and the trends on Google search (public discourse).

This entire #Lalitgate topic was selling like a hotcake for at least a week or so, starting from June 14, 2015. Ten days news headlines of Times Now, India Today TV and Times of India was especially investigated as these two organizations, BCCL and TV Today Network, locked their horn in a bitter fight to grab the maximum attention through their respective media outlets.

Also to gauge the public discourse the Google Trend was analyzed between June and July 2015, as the trending topics are more likely to be searched.

TWITTER

The # (hashtags) a potent weapon for trolling!

The # symbol, called a hashtag, is used to mark keywords or phrase (no spaces) in a Tweet and are often trending topics. It was created organically by Twitter users as a way to categorize messages. Hashtags can appear anywhere in Tweets. Clicking on a hashtagged word in any message shows all other Tweets marked with that

keyword, this allows one to follow and participate in discussions.

Twitter user's follows people they are interested in and those people's tweets will appear in the user's feed on home page. However, to automatically find out the Tweets written by people whom one not follows, hashtags can be used.

Timeline of News and Social Media Trends for #Lalitgate

June 14, 2015 – The #Lalitgate story was first broadcasted on Times Now. Times Now anchor Arnab Goswami claims that he had the documents of the story of #Lalitgate for about ten days before he sent out the first mail to Sushma Swaraj on June 7 and then again on June 11, 2015. However, since he doesn't get any reply from the minister so he decided to broadcast the story.

June 14, 2015 (2:23 PM) – The immediate reaction came from the anchor of rival channel @rahulkanwal 'India Today TV', "When I first visited Fox News in U.S. I thanked my stars that India didn't have such crazies. Arnab makes Fox look like a sensible channel".

June 14, 2015 (3:24 PM) – Soon follows the another tweet from @rahulkanwal, "@TimesNow was displaced from its perch as No 1 channel by @IndiaToday last week. Desperate tactics to reclaim position by hook or crook?"

June 14, 2015 (4:01 PM) – @sardesairajdeep from 'India Today TV' tweeted, "A story broken by Sunday Times of London and Indian news channels take credit? Surely, we have lost our moral compass again!!"

However Arnab Goswami alleges that "he has the mails from reporters of *The Sunday Times* asking him and his London based reporter for documents on June 13, for more details on the story.

June 14, 2015 (5:40 PM) – @LalitKModi choose to reply on the twitter; "This is regard an #all day#breaking #news #story in #india and#uk - <http://m.timesofindia.com/videos/news/Visa-row-Lalit-Modi-refuses-to-respond/videoshow/47666388.cms>". I guess @timesnow choose to differentiate what's #verbatim. I choose to give you what I call #verbatim. Now you know who tells verbatim and who chooses to cut and paste what they like. When I actually respond to this story - all who are saying what they are will either #laugh all the way with a big (smily) and most will likely #hide or duck for#cover. That will be fun to watch. Till then for me it's (smily)

June 15, 2015 – @LalitKModi retorted on the twitter;

"Press conference will be conducted by mr Mehmood abdi at 8 pm this evening. The press conference is at the Fourseasons hotel worli Mumbai". (Mehmood Abdi is the lawyer of Lalit Modi.)

"Media globally will not want to miss this press conference. It will be full expose with facts, documentation and hard data. No hearsay".

"Congress party should be watching this press conference. So should all who have jumped up and down in last few years."

"Only thing I want to point out that mr chidambaram, shashi tharoor, Salman Khursheed and erstwhile PMO. Should watch this press briefing."

"This story will turn in its head I can assure you all right now. Let's wait and watch who was on the right and who was in the wrong."

"Lastly before I board another flight to another beautiful destination. This is war. So bring it on. I choose to lose a battle to win a war."

Today was just a teaser. Tomorrow night going live and exclusive myself with @sardesairajdeep in person from #montenegro - see u tom here

June 16, 2015 – Rajdeep Sardesai went to Montenegro to interview Lalit Modi as this was the biggest news break of 2015.

June 23, 2015 – @LalitKModi "So all those are on a witch hunt - time to know you all live in (a) glass house. By the way I document every meeting when someone asks for a bribe and I circulate to my lawyers xyz has asked for this in exchange for this. Off course I never paid. But record I did"

The Twitter handle @LalitKModi became a hot-spot and has got 400,000 new followers in addition to 500,000 two weeks ago when Sushma Swaraj's help to him was first revealed.

On **June 22, 2015**, when @LalitKModi was trending not only in India but also in the UK, entrepreneur Gaurav Wankhede who had been following his tweets all day seemed tired and wrote: "@LalitKModi, when will you let us go to sleep, it's 2:20 am here in India." Modi shot back: "In time of war the general never sleeps. You have to be ready for the unexpected."

Lalit Modi effectively used the Twitter to sensationalize the issue, make the audience wanting more, tempting them with lines such as "See date carefully. Keep at the back of your head" and asking them to remember names mentioned in tweets to link to information he will provide later.

The followers of Modi were not only from common spectators but also from the corridors of power. A line added to his Twitter profile, "Busy cleaning Political Mafia", got everyone hooked. Even ministers and politicians were reportedly logging in to check the Tweets from @LalitKModi. The person who is wanted by the Enforcement Directorate for economic offences and who has had his passport revoked earlier, became a self-declared advocate against corruption in politics. Declaring war on his rivals, Modi said he was a master at it. "I did not start this war. But I am master at the art of war. So now don't blame me for collateral damage. That's just what war does," he tweeted.

Mainstream media including the largest selling English daily Times of India, were quick to pick the story. <http://>

After this his profile was changed to following image:

Lalit Kumar Modi

@LalitKModi

Worker @ Fightcorruption.org. Founder and architect @IPL Indian Premier League & @CLT20, President RCA, President Modi Enterprises modi.com

London, England · lalitmodi.com

timesofindia.indiatimes.com/ reported the story with following headlines:

Row over Sushma Swaraj helping Lalit Modi: IPL factional feud back in the spotlight Lalit Modi: The man nobody now wants to be seen with Row over Sushma Swaraj helping Lalit Modi: Rajnath, RSS stand by foreign minister

Sushma Swaraj helped get UK travel documents for 'fugitive' Lalit Modi

Keith Vaz faces probe for aid to Lalit Modi, but defends his act

June 20, 2015, Lalit Modi again took the nation by storm through his series of tweets. First he Tweeted "Request

ews channels in India, account for just 0.7 per cent of total TV p. Hindi news channels in contrast make up for about 3.3 per cent nal news 3.6 per cent of the total Viewership Share by Genre (2013). media in India is driven by perception. The correlation between and rating is the highest in English news. That explains why in spite 1 fraction of the total news consumption, it got a disproportionately 00 crore of the Rs 3,000 crore that advertisers spent on news TV in : media coverage of Lalit Modi was also a war to grab the maximum

very interesting relation between the critical issues and the public , which can be observe using the feature of Google Trends. Times the channel which got maximum mileage in #Lalitgate, and a higher icking in Google trends as well.

THE RANKING GAME

Average time spent by a viewer in a day

	Week 21	Week 22	Week 23
India Today Television	00:02:36	00:04:31	00:02:37
Times Now	00:08:03	00:04:27	00:04:52
CNN IBN	00:04:43	00:04:37	00:04:00
NDTV 24x7	00:02:23	00:04:31	00:03:02
News X	00:07:40	00:15:53	00:03:44

Rating (in 000*, across 30 minute average)

**Reach (% coverage)

Viewer is defined as individual in this data versus last week's where the viewer was defined as a household. Therefore, time spent and reach data differ. *Rating - If India Today TV's rating is 151, it means 151000 men of the age 22 plus in the defined geography watched India Today TV averaged across 30 minutes. All India (Iiac*) Male 22 + NCS AB; **Reach is the percentage of viewers who watched the channel in a given week

ALL #MEDIA #PEOPLE #OWNERS - who have #taken MY @IPL @bcci #hospitality Kindly #disclose. The #value of it. And how many times." After that he dared to the owner of TOI group Vineet Jain "similarly its my #duty too. #vineetjain of #Toi please advise all concerned of what u took #specifically. In my #books it amounts to a very large cost. As all #tickets were paid for by someone else or me #facilitated that cost. All on file"

On the media coverage he again retorted through his Tweets "If one were to switch on any#TV #channel in #india - it seems as if some #people have a lot of time. I have said my piece to @sardesairajdeep watch it on line anytime at indiatoday.com - one thing to always remember - #truth shall always #surface. In #india it takes a little longer. As one must go thru #trial by media. Then the#legal route where #deferment after#deferment happens. But #ultimately the#honorable #courts when given the chance - do eventually rule. One day #india too will have new #legislationthat will make #false #reporting - a thing of the past and #responsible #media will be the order of the day like in#unitedkingdom and other countries. Till then we can continue to watch #reality tv at its #best. Lot of noise little#substance. One needs to #pardon the ignorance of some of #india's past #rulers. They are jobless. Atleast one knows now that only one can get any media

attention ONLY IF THEY use the #modi name and so they can get there one minute on media is guaranteed. That used to be the case with another NameG... Forget it why give them another second to appear in media.

A channel's rating is a function of three things: **Reach**, **Switching to the Channel** and the **Time Spent** on it. Reach depends on the distribution; switching to a particular channel is a function of brand pull, and the actual time spent on it

Discussion and Conclusion:

Twitter is one of the prime sources of news gathering. Its authenticity and ability to create dialogue have converted it into a potent tool used by source and the medium, the two important elements of communication.

Largely the same set of people, who were following Modi on the twitter and searching him on the google, were also interested in watching news about him and Tweeting their response to both Lalit Modi and the Media.

Lalit Modi was successful in putting his point in the public domain using Twitter, believing that he is the one who is setting the agenda of the day, but the last laugh was of the other side, who were busy garnering the juice from the both end, raising the TRP as well earning the revenues.

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